

OAPEN Foundation 2021 Stakeholder Report

Key Results and Developments

open
2021

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The OAPEN Foundation's mission to increase discoverability and trust for open access books has guided us through yet another year marked by the pandemic. While the global community was faced with lockdowns and severe restrictions, we saw a significant usage increase of the thousands of open access (OA) books available through the OAPEN Library and the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB). The pandemic has indeed emphasised the need for OA and the importance of OA to scholarly content.

As open infrastructures selected by SCOSS (The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services) OAPEN and DOAB attracted more support from [institutions and consortia](#) across the globe in 2021. Thanks to the visibility and campaigning efforts in collaboration with SCOSS we were able to reach an important funding milestone for our organisation, reaching our SCOSS funding target halfway through 2021. The SCOSS funding campaign has been incredibly helpful for kickstarting and building connections with the library community, while the financial support of these 89 institutions from 14 countries directly contributes to the development of our services and sustained operations.

We are thankful for and appreciate the continued support we have seen from the library community following the funding milestone. In 2021, we saw our total library supporter base nearly double to 165 libraries that now support our services via various routes. This continued support remains crucial for the further development of our services, enabling us to deliver on our mission while global interest in OA books continues to grow.

This annual stakeholder report will show you how we engage in the global transition to OA books and how our infrastructures support the many exciting initiatives that have surfaced recently in the OA books landscape. We are very grateful to play a role in this vibrant playing field and would like to thank all our library supporters, contributing publishers and research funders, and all other partners that we have worked with in 2021, and still work with, for wonderful collaboration, for your support and trust in us.

It is such an exciting time for open access book publishing.

PS: While writing this introduction, the Russian invasion of Ukraine continues. Our thoughts and our sincere wishes for this terrible war to stop go to the Ukrainian people. Concretely, we – as a core and founding member of OPERAS – have signed the OPERAS statement on initiatives and measures to support Ukraine's social sciences and humanities community <https://operas.hypotheses.org/5109>.

OAPEN Library

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/31387>

174,380 downloads

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/26277>

37,525 downloads

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/29557>

31,412 downloads

Most downloaded books

All books and chapters in the OAPEN Library are available for direct download without any cost or registration requirements for the user. **In 2021, we have added 4,600 publications** to the OAPEN Library, increasing the size of the complete collection to well over 19,000 open access books. In terms of publishers, we have welcomed 75 new publishers to the OAPEN Library publisher community, consisting of 400+ publishers now.

OAPEN: Collection Growth and Publishers

Number of downloads

The OAPEN Library is being widely used and accessed by users globally. In 2021, we saw an impressive increase in the number of downloads. During this period, the collection grew from around 14,500 to more than 19,000 books. At the same time, **downloads from the OAPEN Library increased by 127% in 2021** to well over 11 million COUNTER-conformant downloads annually. Corrected for collection growth, this resulted in the average book seeing about 74% more downloads per title.

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/32834>

27,308 downloads

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/23012>

24,522 downloads

Most downloaded books

Languages and Licenses

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/31235>

21,925 downloads

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/31077>

19,872 downloads

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/35002>

19,746 downloads

Most downloaded books

License distribution

Language distribution

Number of libraries engaging with the OAPEN Library

Taking a closer look at how libraries engage with the OAPEN Library, our analysis showed that when examining data for 2021, over 1,100 academic institutions and libraries have used the OAPEN Library. Patrons at these libraries and academic institutions access the OAPEN Library via the library catalogue, discovery systems, or other third-party systems and routes. More information: <https://oapen.hypotheses.org/246>.

Research funders and collections

The OAPEN Library is home to fourteen open access book collections of research funders, publisher collectives and open access initiatives. The collections are carefully managed by the OAPEN team. As small subsets of the entire OAPEN Library, the collections provide the research funders with depositing, hosting, distribution, discoverability, preservation, and reporting services. We were pleased to introduce a new collection in 2021, thanks to an exciting collaboration with CERN's SCOAP³ for Books Initiative (the Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics). This collaboration will result in over 100 important books in the discipline of particle physics to be added to the SCOAP³ for Books collection in the OAPEN Library. As part of the ERC-OAPEN-2019 project (<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/964352>) we have engaged in exciting discussions with several research funders about establishing a trusted forum for research funders, focusing on the development and sustainability of the OAPEN infrastructure and service provision.

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/39979>

19,599 downloads

<https://library.oapen.org/handle/20.500.12657/39979>

19,179 downloads

Most downloaded books

Directory of Open Access Books

Since 2012, the OAPEN Foundation has operated the global indexing service, the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB, <http://doabooks.org>). In 2019, DOAB was created as a not-for-profit Dutch Foundation owned by OAPEN and OpenEdition (<https://www.openedition.org>) through Aix-Marseille University (<https://www.univ-amu.fr/en>) and CNRS (<https://www.cnrs.fr/en>).

Today DOAB indexes over 50,000 peer-reviewed OA books from more than 550 publishers. All metadata in DOAB is distributed fully open (CC0) from its open source DSpace 6 platform in several formats including MARC, CSV, RIS and ONIX. It is also possible to search the directory using the REST API and the directory can be harvested using OAI-PMH.

DOAB is free to use for libraries and publishers and anyone else. Users don't need to register to explore the richness of the catalogue. Publishers need to comply with basic requirements for peer review and open licensing to have their books indexed in DOAB.

Libraries and other institutions (including research funders) can support the operation and development of DOAB through our membership programme and publishers can support DOAB through our sponsorship programme. We wish to thank all our [supporters](#) and [sponsors](#) immensely for their contributions in 2021.

DOAB Supervisory Board and Management

The DOAB Foundation is managed by the Executive Board: Pierre Mounier (Associate Director of OpenEdition and co-coordinator of OPERAS) and Niels Stern (Director of OAPEN Foundation) and steered by a Supervisory Board:

- Neil Jacobs - Chair (UK Reproducibility Network)
- Bas Savenije (OAPEN Foundation)
- Lionel Maurel (CNRS)
- Lucinda Jones (National Library of the Netherlands)
- Fabien Borget (Aix-Marseille University)

Growth of titles and publishers

Around **12,000 new titles** and over 100 new publishers were added to the Directory of Open Access Books (DOAB) throughout 2021. This includes new publishers from countries such as Costa Rica, Denmark, Ecuador, Singapore and many other: resulting in DOAB indexing over 48,000 OA books and chapters from around 550 publishers by the end of the year 2021.

DOAB Trusted Platform Network & SciELO Books

DOAB introduced a new partnership with SciELO Books: enhancing the discoverability of Latin American open access books while creating a more seamless process for publishers to list their open access books in DOAB. Through this new initiative, SciELO Books becomes part of a group of several trusted platforms: The DOAB Trusted Platform Network (<https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/doab-trusted-platform-network>). This network collaborates on improving the discoverability of open access books.

Languages and Licenses

License distribution

Language distribution

DOAB Scientific Committee and PRISM

DOAB Scientific Committee:

- Lucy Montgomery – Chair (Curtin University, Australia)
- Abrizah Abdullah (Universiti Malaya, Malaysia)
- Anne Baillot (CNRS, France)
- Cherifa Boukacem (Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, France)
- Didier Torny (CNRS, France)
- Eelco Ferwerda (Independent consultant, Netherlands)
- Enrico Pasini (Università degli Studi di Torino, Italy)
- Gilberto Hochman (Fundação Oswaldo Cruz, Brazil)
- Janneke Adema (Coventry University, UK)
- Kamel Belhamef (Université Abderrahmane Mira – Bejaia, Algeria)
- Kathleen Fitzpatrick (Michigan State University, USA)
- Lars Bjørnshauge (DOAJ, UK)

In 2021, we renamed the DOAB ‘Certification Service’ to ‘Peer Review Information Service for Monographs’ (PRISM – <https://doabooks.org/en/publishers/prism>) since the service is intended to provide information about the quality assurance process of publishers. PRISM allows publishers to share with readers and authors information about their peer review process in a standardised way. The information provided becomes part of the metadata of the book and will be displayed as a hyperlinked label attached to the book and the publisher. The goal of the service is to support trust in OA book publishing, by improving transparency around the quality assurance of OA book publishers and their books.

During 2021 and (2022/Q1), the PRISM service and workflow has been tested with various publishers and feedback from those tests has led to some adjustments. Following the tests and adjustments, internal onboarding workflows will be set up and the onboarding is then expected to begin in 2022/Q3.

DOAB has set up a **Scientific Committee** (established June 2021) to help and advise the DOAB Executive Board and the Supervisory Board on scientific matters and to monitor the development and implementation of PRISM.

OASPA Membership

In 2021, DOAB officially became a member of OASPA (<https://oaspa.org>), a mission-driven organisation which encourages and enables open access as the predominant model of communication for scholarly outputs, representing a diverse community of organisations engaged in open scholarship. Up until 2021, its membership was covered by the OAPEN Foundation.

We specifically look forward to supporting independent publication venues and bibliodiversity in academic book publishing together with OASPA. A blog post elaborating on our motivations to become an OASPA member can be found here (<https://oaspa.org/welcoming-doab-as-an-oaspa-member/>).

Sponsorships

With the further development and growth of DOAB, we have also updated our DOAB sponsorship scheme in 2021. The DOAB sponsorship programme invites organisations that endorse and support a transition to open access for books. In 2021, all existing DOAB sponsors (the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation; De Gruyter; and Springer Nature) continued their support of our services. We were also pleased to welcome Taylor & Francis (Gold sponsor) and OCLC (Bronze sponsor) on board as new sponsors this year. We are thankful for these sponsorship contributions that directly support the DOAB platform and help maintain and further develop a trusted venue dedicated to open access books. All sponsors are publicly acknowledged on our website and receive additional benefits depending on their sponsorship level.

SPRINGER NATURE

OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit

2021 also saw new members of the Editorial Advisory Board which now consists of:

- Niels Stern – Chair (Director OAPEN Foundation & Co-director DOAB Foundation)
- Lotte Kruijt – main contact (Project Manager, OAPEN Foundation)
- Margo Bargheer (Head of Electronic Publishing, Göttingen University Press)
- Lucy Barnes (Editor and Outreach Coordinator, Open Book Publishers)
- Jan Bergstra (Guest Researcher, University of Amsterdam)
- Christina Emery (Senior Marketing Manager, Thought Leadership Programmes, Springer Nature)
- Eelco Ferwerda (Independent consultant)
- Kevin Hawkins (Assistant Dean for Scholarly Communication, University of North Texas Libraries)
- Andrew Joseph (Digital Publisher, Wits University Press)
- Koen Leurs (Assistant Professor Gender & Postcolonial Studies, Utrecht University)
- Valerie McCutcheon (Research Information Manager, University of Glasgow)
- Lucy Montgomery (Professor of Knowledge Innovation, Curtin University)
- Sotiria Psoma (University Lecturer BioScience and Technology, The Open University)
- Ros Pyne (Global Director, Research and Open Access, Bloomsbury)
- Claire Redhead (Executive Director, OASPA)
- Jeroen Sondervan (Project Leader Open Access & Open Science Programme, Utrecht University)
- Graham Stone (Subject Specialist - Open Access Monographs, Jisc)

The OAPEN OA Books Toolkit (<https://oabooks-toolkit.org/>) is a community-developed and stakeholder-agnostic information resource for OA books that was launched in 2020. It is operated and coordinated by OAPEN and supported by an Editorial Advisory Board with a multi-stakeholder representation chaired by OAPEN. During 2021, the toolkit has been widely adopted by the OA books community, particularly by academic libraries and research support teams at universities. Since its introduction, it has been used about 25,000 times by more than 15,000 users from over 172 countries. In 2021, all articles have been revised adding licence information and new information for many articles. New articles are in the pipeline, but already in late 2021, an article on the relationship between OA books and Open Educational Resources was added.

The OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit covers specific topics related to open access books. Each article offers a quick and brief introduction to a particular aspect of open access book publishing. The toolkit also serves as a signposting tool: articles include a list of sources referenced, further reading and links to definitions of key terms.

Research life cycle

The toolkit makes use of a typical research lifecycle, consisting of the following eight stages. Click on each stage to find related articles.

- ▶ Planning and Funding
- ▶ Conduct Research
- ▶ Consider Publishing Options
- ▶ Write & submit manuscript
- ▶ Peer review
- ▶ Book contract and License
- ▶ Book is published & disseminated
- ▶ Research is reused

Open Access Books Network

In 2021, OAPEN continued with its contribution to the Open Access Books Network (OABN) by providing one of its three coordinators. In its second year, the OABN further grew its global community and online presence. The OABN created its own online presence through channels such as YouTube & Zenodo and held conference presentations, created new videos, blog materials, and organised events. Find out more here: <https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/2021/12/15/making-new-connections-year-two-of-the-oabn/#more-360>

20 21 OABN

A year of spreading wings

986 Twitter followers
38 YouTube subscribers
307 HC members
110 Slack channel members
209 mailing list subscribers

10 blog posts
17 YouTube videos
2 print interviews
1.139 YouTube views

4 OA Books Workouts sessions
5 Voices workshops
4 OA Mythbusters videos
4 OA Bookmarks sessions
2 conference presentations

COMMUNITY CONTRIBUTORS

OPERAS	MEDIASTUDIES.PRESS
OASPA	COPIM
OATP	UCT LIBRARY
CAMBRIDGE UNIVERSITY LIBRARY	DARIAH-EU
KU LEUVEN LIBRARY	THE CONTINENTAL PLATFORM

We would like to thank fellow-OABN coordinators Agata Morka (SPARC Europe) and Lucy Barnes (Open Book Publishers) for their continued efforts helping the OABN to thrive.

One of these event series brought together over 450 participants representing a wide group of OA book stakeholders

One of these event series, voices from the OA books community (<https://openaccessbooksnetwork.hcommons.org/voices-from-the-oa-books-community/>), brought together over 450 participants representing a wide group of OA book stakeholders to discuss 'what a Plan S for books should look like?' in the form of five workshops. OAPEN hosted one of these workshops on the topic of Green OA for books.

Looking ahead, the OABN will become its own OPERAS Special Interest Group in 2022. With the support of OPERAS, the OABN will be able to better serve and connect with actors from the European SSH landscape around open access books.

Community engagement and communication

OAPEN is an active participant in conversations on open access book publishing around the world. OAPEN organised and participated in events such as (virtual) conferences, workshops, and webinar sessions. Next to this, OAPEN uses its communication channels to inform and engage with its community via blogs, twitter, and mailing lists.

9 blogs
12k+ total blog visits

1,134 new followers
11,674 total followers
299k+ total tweet views

16 newsletters
3,875 total subscribers
601 new subscribers

27 total events

OPERAS on ESFRI roadmap

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) Committee announced on 30 June 2021 that OPERAS, the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area (<https://www.operas-eu.org>) would be added to the ESFRI Roadmap 2021 (<https://www.esfri.eu/latest-esfri-news/new-ris-roadmap-2021>). OAPEN is a founding member of OPERAS and represented in the OPERAS Executive Assembly.

This was a very important milestone for OPERAS on its road to become an ERIC (European Research Infrastructure Consortium). The decision confirms that OPERAS is officially recognised by the 27 member states of the European Union as a key research infrastructure with excellent scientific value and sufficient maturity. ESFRI is a strategic instrument to develop the scientific integration of Europe and to strengthen its international outreach. Being selected for the ESFRI Roadmap is a high-level recognition for a European Research Infrastructure.

OPERAS-NL national node

OAPEN is the national node for OPERAS in the Netherlands. On 22nd June 2021, the first national node event in the Netherlands (OPERAS-NL) was arranged. This online event marked the start of OPERAS-NL and brought together actors part of the Dutch open scholarly community in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) to discuss how OPERAS can help advance the transition to Open Science in the SSH. With about 25 participants we discussed the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, why OPERAS is important to the SSH community in the Netherlands, learned about experiences with OPERAS in France, and reflected on its relations to the Netherlands. Furthermore, this event served to gather input around three main questions helping further shape OPERAS and its engagement in the Netherlands:

- How do you think OPERAS can add value to the Dutch SSH landscape?
- Who should OPERAS partner up with?
- What would you like to know more about (OPERAS Service, etc.)?

A complete overview of all the suggestions can be found publicly here: shorturl.at/dryzB

Annual Meeting for Supporting Libraries (stakeholder committee)

In 2021, OAPEN participated in the following groups and fora:

OPERAS Executive Assembly

OPERAS national node for the Netherlands

Think.Check.Submit committee

OASPA OA books interest group

OAEU advisory board

Crossref books interest group

SCOSS

OABN

*Netherlands Enterprise Agency
Stakeholder Board*

In November 2021, we organised the Annual Meeting for Supporting Libraries. This annual event served to gather input, ideas and feedback from our library community. In total, more than 40 participants took part in this annual exercise, contributing to the shaping of our organisation and technical roadmap.

During this meeting we also introduced the first DOAB-OAPEN library working group. This new and informal group will be implemented in 2022. Through this body, we will be collaborating with experts from the library community to advise and work with us on better embedding open access books within the library ecosystem: addressing key issues and challenges that open access books currently face.

Articles published

Avanço, K., Balula, A. et al. (2021). Future of Scholarly Communication. Forging an inclusive and innovative research infrastructure for scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705>

Ferwerda, E., Mosterd, T., Snijder, R., & Mounier, P. (2021). UKRI Gap Analysis of Open Access Monographs Infrastructure. UKRI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5735021>

Snijder, R. (2021). Open access book usage data – how close is COUNTER to the other kind? Insights, 34(1), 9. <https://doi.org/10.1629/uksg.539>

Snijder, R. (2021). Words Algorithm Collection—Finding closely related open access books using text mining techniques. LIBER Quarterly: The Journal of the Association of European Research Libraries, 31(1). <https://doi.org/10.53377/lq.10938>

Stern, N. (2021). A brief saga about open access books. Nordic Perspectives on Open Science. <https://doi.org/10.7557/11.5751>

OAPEN also contributed to two important documents for OA books in 2021. Firstly, Niels Stern was a co-editor of the paper 'Investing in the Open Access Book infrastructure - A call for action' (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4768387>) and co-author of the cOAlition S blog post 'Accelerating open access to academic books' (<https://www.coalition-s.org/blog/accelerating-open-access-to-academic-books/>) which reflects on the important cOAlition S statement on open access to academic books (<https://www.coalition-s.org/coalition-s-statement-on-open-access-for-academic-books/>) issued in September 2021.

Conference presentations & events

Knowledge Exchange workshop on 'Investment in Open Access Book Infrastructure'

UKRI Stakeholder workshop as part of 'UKRI Gap Analysis of Open Access Monograph Infrastructure'

Open Access Books Network BoOkmArks session on 'The Continental Platform: OA Publishing in Africa'

National Open Science Festival 2021 Netherlands, 'How to publish your book in open access – testing the OA Books Toolkit'

Joint workshop by OPERAS-P & OASPA on 'Non-BPC business models for OA books – Punctum Books & Open Book Publishers'

Joint workshop by OPERAS-P & OASPA on 'Innovative business models for OA books – 6 approaches in Europe'

Joint workshop by OPERAS-P & OASPA on 'Non-BPC business models for OA books - COPIM, Opening the Future'

Charleston Conference 2021 presentation 'Integrating Open Access Books into the Acquisitions and Cataloging Process'

OPERAS-GER Workshop 'Peer review of open access books – increasing transparency using the OPERAS Certification Service'

TRIPLE Conference 2021 presentation 'Business & Open Science – Contrast or complement?'

Charleston Conference 2021 presentation 'From usage reporting to OA Analytics: how OA usage data is transforming scholarly communications decision-making across publishers and libraries'

Open Access Tage 2021 presentation 'How Open Infrastructure Benefits Libraries'

ARMA Conference 2021 presentation 'Open Access Toolkit for Books'

OpenScience Fair 2021 'Open Access Toolkit for Books'

OASPA Conference 2021 presentation 'DOAB Certification Service – increasing transparency of peer review practices'

Association of Brazilian University Presses meeting (ABEU) 2021 presentation 'Open Access Books: A collaborative approach / Livros de Acesso Aberto: o triunfo da colaboratividade'

OAPEN has engaged in the global conversation on open access books by giving presentations and participating in panels at conferences and webinars across the world

LIBER 2021 Conference, LIBER & OASPA Workshop 'A shared future for open access books – exploring partnerships between libraries and publishers'

LIBER 2021 Conference presentation 'How can Open Infrastructure Support the Role of Research Libraries?'

OPERAS-NL 2021 National Event workshop 'Building Research Infrastructures and Communities for Open Scholarly Communications in the Humanities and Social Sciences'

SCOAP3 Governing Council meeting: 'OAPEN and the SCOAP3 for Books Pilot'

Open Access Books Network Workshop 'Voices from the OA Books Community – Green Open Access Books'

Jisc & SCOSS webinar presentation 'Sustaining the future of key open research infrastructure services (SCOSS)'

SSP 2021 Annual Meeting Session 'Forging a Path Forward: How three Non-profit Aggregators are Working Together to Support the Future of the OA monograph'

Open Access Network presentation 'Publishing your Book in Open Access'

UKSG 2021 Conference presentation 'Empowering universities and researchers: Two practical toolkits for New-University-Press and Open Access Book Publishing'

LIBER Webinar presentation 'How can libraries help keep Open Science infrastructures free and independent?'

New technical features and functionalities

We have been working on further integrating our technical environment. On top of that, we have introduced new features and functionalities.

DOAB DSpace migration

In February 2021, DOAB migrated to the same platform as the OAPEN Library: the collection is hosted using DSpace 6 and the website is maintained using Strapi. From now on, both DOAB and OAPEN offer the same functionalities. Strapi is a CMS licensed under the MIT License. DSpace is typically used for creating open access repositories for scholarly digital content and is supported by a large and global user base.

Selective export and KBART format

In 2021, we introduced a new metadata format: KBART. Adding the KBART export format to both DOAB and the OAPEN Library has been requested by the library community. In addition to the KBART format we have introduced a 'selective export' function to export books and chapters in a flexible way: first by selecting the relevant titles and secondly by choosing the export format.

More information can be found here: <https://oopen.hypotheses.org/261>.

Technical roadmap

We shared a technical roadmap with our library members, as a way to discuss the ongoing development of the infrastructure. Among the developments listed are metadata improvements and document ingestion for both OAPEN and DOAB, a full text search functionality for the OA Books Toolkit, and the development of a usage dashboard for libraries, publishers, and funders.

Input/output chart

Both the publishers we work with, and the users of our collection are diverse and may have different technical requirements. Our current technical environment reflects this diversity. It enables publishers to add their books, chapters, and metadata in a variety of ways. Also, by offering several types of metadata output, we ensure that the OAPEN and DOAB collections reach readers, teachers, researchers, and libraries.

OPERAS-P

copim

Triple

scelc

European Research Council, ERC-OAPEN-2019
(EU - <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/964352>)

UKRI gap analysis
(UK - <https://zenodo.org/record/5735021>)

OPERAS-P finalised
(EU - <https://www.operas-eu.org/projects/operas-p/>)

OPERAS-NL (NL)

University Presses and OA books in NL
(supported by OPuS Foundation) (NL)

COPIM
(UK - <https://www.copim.ac.uk/>)

TRIPLE
(EU - <https://project.gotriple.eu/>)

SCELC & OAPEN Pilot Project
(U.S. - <https://scelc.libguides.com/SCELC-OAPEN>)

Open Access eBook Usage (OAeBU) Data Trust pilot project
(U.S. - https://educopia.org/data_trust/)

OPERAS-P: Grant agreement 871069

TRIPLE: Grant agreement 863420

ERC: Grant agreement 964352

OAPEN Foundation Boards and Management

The OAPEN Foundation is a not-for-profit organisation based in the Netherlands, with its registered office at the National Library in The Hague. OAPEN is dedicated to open access, peer-reviewed books. OAPEN operates three platforms:

- OAPEN Library - a central repository for hosting and disseminating OA books
- OAPEN Open Access Books Toolkit - a toolkit on OA book publishing for authors
- Directory of Open Access Books - a discovery service indexing OA books, in partnership with OpenEdition

OAPEN Board of Directors

The OAPEN Foundation is managed by a Board of Directors which was extended with two new members in 2021: Lidia Borrell-Damiàn and Charles Watkinson. We are very pleased to welcome our new Board members. The OAPEN Board of Directors consists of the following members:

- Bas Savenije (Chair)
- Kurt De Belder (Secretary) – Leiden University
- Reinier Groen (Treasurer)
- Antia Wiersma – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
- Lidia Borrell-Damiàn – Science Europe
- Charles Watkinson – University of Michigan Press

OAPEN Advisory Board

In 2021, the Board of Directors agreed to set up an Advisory Board. The role of the Advisory Board is to provide the Board of Directors with solicited and unsolicited advice on the business matters of OAPEN. The Advisory Board also has the right to render a binding nomination for one member of the OAPEN Board of Directors.

The Advisory Board comprises members from different stakeholder groups and geographical regions. The members are:

- Dirk Pieper, Deputy Director, Bielefeld University Library
- Natalia Grygierczyk, Director, Radboud University Press
- Claire Redhead, Director, OASPA
- Regula Graf, Scientific Officer, Swiss National Science Foundation
- Wendy Queen, Director, Project MUSE
- Marin Dacos, National Open Science Coordinator, Ministry of Science
- Carsten Buhr, Managing Director, De Gruyter
- Agnès Ponsati, CSIC - Unit of Information Resources for Research, Director (Spanish National Research Council)

OAPEN Team

The OAPEN team as of 1 January 2022:

- Niels Stern, Director
stern@oapen.org
- Ronald Snijder, Deputy Director
r.snijder@oapen.org
- Lotte Kruijt, Project Manager
l.kruijt@oapen.org
- Dorien van der Giessen, Collection Manager
d.vandergiessen@oapen.org
- Tom Mosterd, Community Manager
t.mosterd@oapen.org

In 2021, the OAPEN Foundation had a net positive financial result, allowing us to commence with the building of a contingency fund to support operations for a minimum of 12 months, in line with the Principles for Open Scholarly Infrastructures. In financial terms we saw a positive balance in 2021 of 142,611 EUR, based on net turnover of 562,053 EUR

Net Turnover

Costs

We will continue to build new services to advance the development of more open access to books to the benefit of researchers and readers in general

The increased growth of the OAPEN Library and DOAB requires our full attention. We want to make sure that new publishers are onboarded well and experience the benefits of being distributed through our infrastructures. Wide and seamless distribution of high quality and fully open metadata is core to fulfil our mission of increased discoverability of OA books. From this operational base, we will continue in 2022 to build new services for the academic libraries, publishers, and research funders to advance the development of more open access to books to the benefit of researchers and readers in general.

Library Working Group

We are excited to engage with our newly established Library Working Group in 2022. The purpose of this working group is to stay aligned with the needs of the academic libraries, not least in a technical sense, which is why we share our technical roadmap with libraries to invite for feedback and input. For instance, together with the library community we have identified three areas where we will focus our attention first:

- Advocating for flagging and coverage of open access books in library acquisition systems, including open access books in existing library workflows for acquiring (e)books
- Ensuring timely inclusion of open access books and quality coverage of their metadata in library & discovery systems
- Increasing awareness and availability of open access books

Usage statistics dashboards

One of the new services that we will launch in 2022 will be a dashboard service providing usage data to publishers hosted by the OAPEN Library, research funders that we provide services to (collection management) and supporting libraries. At launch, the dashboard will display monthly updated COUNTER-conformant download data

We will draw the first lines of a strategy to become more global

from the OAPEN Library in a user-friendly way. However, we want to explore further with the community the kind of data that will be of interest to the different stakeholders in the years to come. This input will be important to our development plans.

Global OA book community engagement

As mentioned above, we have been immensely grateful for the support we have received from many libraries around the world. Our promise and our goal are to sustain our engagement with the library community. In 2021, we saw important support coming from the USA and Germany which indeed was a focus area for us last year. In 2022, we will keep this focus intact to strengthen our relationships with institutions in these countries, but we will also draw the first lines of a strategy to become more global. We work with many publishers in Europe and North America and increasingly also in South America and to a lesser extent in Asia. We would like to see publishers from more parts of the world making use of our services. Already, we can see a lot of usage (of for instance DOAB) in countries like India, Nigeria and the Philippines although we don't work with publishers in these countries. With the help of our boards and committees and the wider community we hope to be able to take steps in that direction.

Furthermore, we look forward to the launch of the Open Book Collective as an output of the COPIIM project (<https://copim.pubpub.org/open-book-collective>). We hope to see this as a way of strengthening OA book publishing initiatives overall and to help us create relationships to new libraries.

The above headlines are just a few of the initiatives that we foresee for 2022 and that we find important. If you have ideas or suggestions for activities or technical development that you think we should consider, then please do send us an email (info@oapen.org). It is pivotal to us that we stay relevant to all the stakeholders that we work with. We look forward to engaging with you all in 2022!

Yours sincerely,

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